
Deliverable D3.5

Software Forum Research Roadmap v3

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Abstract:	<p>There have been three iterations of this roadmap. The first iteration includes the scoring methodology; valorising the software technology, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity research and innovation roadmap as well as the necessary steps for its implementation. A preliminary set of research priorities were identified, including the input from the cross-fertilisation workshops, the industry, the desktop research performed and the landscape reports from task 3.1. This roadmap has been made available for the open (online) consultation. This iteration is summarised in Deliverable 3.3.</p> <p>The second iteration contains the final set of prioritised research areas, a set of lessons learnt and actions on research priorities for Horizon Europe and Digital Europe. These results have been presented in different events and workshops with the scope of gaining more feedback. Interim and working versions of the roadmaps were used for the cross-fertilisation workshops to foster discussions, gather input and feedback from the whole software community. The results are presented in Deliverable 3.4.</p> <p>The third interaction is presented in this Deliverable 3.5, which, at the same time, confirms previous results and research and consolidates the received feedback. This is the result of Task 3.2.</p>
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Terms and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
DAST	Dynamic Application Security Testing
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
OSS	Open-source Software
OSH	Open-source Hardware
R&I	Research & Innovation
SAST	Static Application Security Testing
SDLC	Software Development LifeCycle
SOLC	Software Operation LifeCycle
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community project

Executive Summary

This document is the third version of a series of three documents. Its aim is to provide policymakers with research and innovation priorities in the field of software technologies, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructures.

To achieve this, a roadmap methodology has been defined in D3.3 - Software Forum Research Roadmap v1 [1], structured in three steps, namely (1) identification of research topics (2) classification and scoring (3) consultation and further analysis. This methodology has been further extended, complemented and some of its phases implemented (identification of research topics, classification, and scoring) in D3.4 - Software Forum Research Roadmap v2 [2]. As a result, in that report **6 research and innovation challenges** for software technologies were identified, characterised, and prioritised against the selected factors. A preliminary set of lessons learnt from the process were presented as a previous step to the policy recommendations.

The current document, D3.5 focuses on the activities related to the third phase of the methodology: open consultation and recommendations. The main objective of this phase has been to get the feedback from the community on the research made and validate previous results from D3.4. In this sense, D3.5 presents the analysis derived from the different consultations performed with the Software community stakeholders, to which the SWForum.eu research and innovation roadmap has been presented. With the results of the analysis of the feedback received and the concluding remarks obtained, a set of policy recommendations is proposed.

Preliminary results of the roadmapping exercise have been submitted for publication in the publication in Open Research Europe under the title *“Prioritisation of research challenges in Software Technologies: A multi factor approach”*. This paper is under review process by ORE.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This document is the third of a series of three documents that aims to present research and innovation challenges in the field of software technologies, including open-source software, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructures.

This Deliverable presents the results of the third and final iteration, aiming to capture feedback from key and related stakeholders and experts. It confirms previous results of the SWForum.eu constituency on the proposed research and innovation Roadmaps (D3.4). The feedback gained has permitted to update the roadmaps and specially to derive the final policy related recommendations. To do so, 3 groups of stakeholders and experts have been selected representing different technology domains, research and innovation projects from SWForum.eu Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and the general audience. Different consultation processes have been implemented with each of the groups. This report describes the open consultation processes implemented and provides the analysis on the feedback collected through them. The analysis has resulted in a set of concluding remarks and related policy recommendations.

Apart from the conclusions and final recommendations, this deliverable also includes all the material developed to implement the consultation processes as well as the raw data collected before the analysis. This content is included as Appendix to this document.

1.2 Document structure

The document is structured in different sections as follows:

Section 1 is the introductory chapter.

Section 2 reviews the roadmapping approach, the methodology followed for the implementation of the research roadmap and details the third phase, “open consultation”, explaining the process followed with each of the selected stakeholders.

Section 3 provides a detailed analysis on the feedback received from the different groups described in section 2.

Section 4 presents the main concluding remarks resulting from the roadmapping exercise implemented in WP3, including the feedback obtained in this open consultation phase.

Section 5 describes the policy related recommendations derived from the concluding remarks in section 4.

Section 6 concludes the document and introduces the next steps.

The **Appendix** section is structured as follows: Appendix A shows the different surveys used within the different open consultation processes carried on. Appendix B provides the new version of the characterisation of the challenges towards the selected factors defined in D3.4 taking into consideration the open consultation feedback.

2 Roadmapping and open consultation approach

2.1 Roadmapping approach

As anticipated, this deliverable, D3.5, is the third and final version of the SWForum.eu research and innovation roadmap, which previous versions were released in December 2021 (D3.3 [1]) and December 2022 (D3.4 [2]). As introduced in D3.3, the main aim of this set of reports is to provide contributions to the European research roadmap in software technologies, including open-source software, digital infrastructure, and cybersecurity, taking into consideration different input sources of information and incorporating the views from different stakeholders such as the industry, independent users and academia.

The methodology followed in SWForum.eu project for the roadmapping can be summarised in three steps, as seen in Figure 1 and described below.

Figure 1. Methodology followed in SWForum.eu for the roadmapping (adapted and extended from [3]). The current document focuses on the phase “Classification and scoring”, hence the different shading in the colours

These three phases were introduced in D3.3, and they cover 1) identification of research topics, 2) classification and scoring and 3) consultation and further analysis.

The focus of this deliverable (D3.5) is phase 3: Consultation and further analysis. As shown in figure 1, the activities performed to implement this phase include:

- ❑ Definition and implementation of several consultation initiatives targeting different stakeholders, such as technology domain experts, workshops attendees, and research and innovation projects.
- ❑ Analysis of the feedback obtained from the different open consultation processes.
- ❑ Update of the prioritisation of research challenges based on the feedback received.
- ❑ Translation of all the information and feedback obtained into the concluding remarks.
- ❑ Determination of the final policy recommendations resulting from the SWForum.eu research and innovation roadmaps.

The open consultation process has been used to collect feedback on the second version of the research and innovation roadmaps, where 6 research and innovation challenges were selected (see figure 2).

Figure 2. SWForum.eu challenges

2.2 Open consultation phase

The SWForum.eu roadmap version 2 (D3.4 [2]) has been subjected to the following three consultation processes (experts consultation, projects consultation, general audience consultation), with different targeted stakeholders aiming to collect feedback from different perspectives:

- **Experts level:** Selected group of technology domains **experts:** These experts were selected based on the six challenges defined in D3.4 (figure 2). For each of the challenges, 3 experts were appointed.
- **Project level:** SWForum.eu is a CSA, conformed by different research and innovation projects in the context of Software Technologies. Those **project experts** related to the challenges have been invited to provide their feedback on the challenges defined.
- **General audience.** The general audience has participated through guided feedback by means of specific tools (i.e., Slido interactive tool) and through ad-hoc inputs, questions and suggestions in the different workshops organised during the lifecycle of the project, and specially, in the last months of the project in the “Concertation and Consultation meeting”¹ held in Brussels in May 2023 and the “SWForum.eu: The Way Forward”² workshop held in Milano June 2023.

2.2.1 Open consultation: Selected group of experts

Eighteen experts have been appointed to review the six challenges of the SWForum.eu roadmap: three experts per challenge as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Open consultation process followed with the Technology specific experts.

The experts were selected from TECNALIA group of researchers in the Digital and Quantum unit. All the people selected was external to the TECNALIA team working in the SWForum.eu project.

Following the SWForum.eu methodology for the consultation process the initial idea was to interview TECNALIA experts. However, due to the difficulties to arrange agendas with all the

¹ <https://www.swforum.eu/events/concertation-and-consultation-computing-continuum-cloud-edge-iot>

² <https://www.swforum.eu/events/swforumeu-way-forward-workshop-future-challenges-software-engineering>

experts, the time needed to perform the 18 interviews and the prerequisite to experts to review the relevant parts of the roadmap version 2 [2] before providing their feedback, the SWForum.eu team decided to collect their feedback through targeted surveys.

Before the survey was launched, the experts were trained during an online session to set up the context and introduce them to the SWForum.eu open consultation exercise (see figure 4).

Figure 4. Screenshot of the online session held with the Technology domain experts for the SWForum.eu open consultation phase.

The surveys used to gather the feedback from experts were created using the European Commission’s open online survey tool, EUSurvey³. A survey was developed for each of the six research and innovation challenges identified (see figure 2)– see Appendix A – Surveys to check all the questions. Each survey is divided into different building blocks of related questions including common questions to all the challenges for further analysis and comparative purposes.

- ❏ The first two questions and the last question (questions 1, 2 and 11) are common to all the surveys.
- ❏ In question 3, each expert must rank topics for the assigned challenge. Each technology expert has been assigned only to one challenge based on her/his expertise and background.
- ❏ Building blocks 3 to 7 cover questions from 4 to 10 which are common to the six challenges. The aim is to assess the assigned challenge and topics against the multi-factor methodology described in detail in phase 2 of the roadmap approach (figure 1) using the same types of questions applied to each of the challenges. Therefore, each expert has answered these questions in relation to the challenge assigned to her/him.

As anticipated, the consultation process started with a training session, that was recorded to explain SWForum.eu project as well as the relevant parts of the roadmap [2]. Experts assessed according to the assigned challenge. An open communication channel using Microsoft Teams was kept open and active to clarify any question and issues that could arise during the process and to store the relevant documents for the consultation process.

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>

Once all the experts completed their assessment through the online survey, the answers were exported to an excel file to perform the analysis – see Appendix A and B for details -. In Section 3 below, the feedback collected from this process is summarised.

2.2.2 Open consultation: SWForum.eu projects

SWForum.eu operates as a Coordination and Support Action under the ICT-50-2020 initiative, and therefore, it supports the Research and Innovation projects (RIAs) funded under that call. Moreover, and as software is a pervasive domain, SWForum.eu community of projects expands across other research topics and calls, creating synergies and promoting liaisons and cross fertilisation activities through projects, specially from: ICT 40 - Cloud Computing, and ICT 56- Next Generation IoT. SWForum.eu project has shared with the community the results gathered regarding the research and innovation roadmaps during the open consultation phase, to get as much feedback possible, from the research community (see figure 5).

ICT-40	Cloud Computing	PHYSICS
		DATA CLOUD
		CHARITY
		SERRANO
		Ai-SPRINT
ICT-56	Next Generation IoT	ASSIST-IoT
		INGENIOUS
		IOT-NGIN
		TERMINET
		INTELLIOT
		VEDLIOT
ICT50	Software Technologies	COSMOS
		ELEGANT
		FOCETA
		PIACERE
		VeriDevOps
		XANDAR

Figure 5. SWForum.eu targeted research and innovation projects in the Open Consultation Phase.

To do so, a survey was sent to the projects under the umbrella of SWForum.eu CSA. These projects' coordinators were requested to answer the survey selecting the challenges on which they have expertise. Each project coordinator could answer more than one different survey according to his/her expertise. The survey was sent to all project coordinators through emails as well as through other dissemination actions that were performed to announce the launch of the survey (see figure 6).

Figure 6. Announcement of the open consultation phase to the projects in the SWForum.eu web page⁴.

Six projects answered the survey, covering different topics from different perspectives. These answers have been incorporated to the analysis presented in section 3.

2.2.3 Open consultation: General Audience

In May 2023, the European Commission (DG CNECT E.2 and E.4 Units) organised the "Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT"⁵ event under the European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum initiative, in collaboration with the OpenContinuum consortium, UNLOCK-CEI and SWForum.eu CSAs (see figure 7).

Figure 7. SWForum.eu coordinator presenting the Research and Innovation Roadmap in the Concertation and Consultation meeting.

This 2-day physical event called took place the 10th and 11th of May in *Brussels, Belgium*. In the event different relevant stakeholders from the Computing were invited to participate and attend. One of the sessions was devoted to present the SWForum.eu research and innovation roadmaps [2] (see figure 7) and to gather feedback through the discussions from the panel and through the following questions collected from the audience via the interactive tool Slido⁶:

- ❏ How do you assess the need to create a European forum and a Software research community covering software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure?
- ❏ Rank from the highest to the lowest priorities the six research and innovation challenges (see Figure 2).
- ❏ Which challenges do you envision in SW engineering for the next 5 years different?

⁴ <https://swforum.eu/news/swforumeu-launches-open-consultation-survey-shape-future-european-software-community>

⁵ <https://swforum.eu/events/concertation-and-consultation-computing-continuum-cloud-edge-iot>

⁶ <https://www.slido.com/>

- ❑ In your opinion, what are the most effective cybersecurity measures/concepts for the computing continuum?
- ❑ Beyond support through investments, is there any regulatory and/or policy action that the Commission should undertake (new) or modify (existing)?

SWForum.eu also organised its own event on the challenges to be addressed in the next future in the context of Software Engineering “SWForum.eu. The Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering”. This event was held in Milan (Italy) on 27th of June and specialists on different topics relevant to software engineering were invited to share their visions (see figure 8). In this case, the event was organised considering the topics and challenges already identified in the version 2, which drove the definition of the programme⁷. The conclusions of the talks and the discussions also contributed to re-shape the research and innovation roadmaps (section 4) and derive the related recommendations presented in section 5.

Figure 8. A Quantum Computing specialist in SWForum.eu The Way Forward workshop.

⁷<https://swforum.eu/agenda-swforumeu-way-forward-workshop-future-challenges-software-engineering>

3 Analysis from the Open Consultation activities

This section presents the results and main outcomes from the analysis performed from the different open consultation activities presented in section 2. The surveys (the answers made to the different stakeholders have been included in the appendices) as well as some extended information about the feedback received (resulting ranking).

3.1 Selected group of experts

SWForum.eu team selected the most appropriate experts for the review of each of the six challenges identified in the roadmap. As anticipated, eighteen TECNALIA experts participated in the consultation process: three experts per challenge. The analysis of this process shows the following results:

- **Most of the experts (89% of them) agreed on the relevance of creating a European forum and a Software research community** covering “*software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure*”.
- All the experts agreed on the **importance of the six challenges** identified in the roadmap. The big majority of them, **89% did not miss any additional challenge** and the remaining 11% of the experts suggested to add the following ones:
 - High Performance Computing
 - Reuse of Software
- With regards to the topics associated to the specific challenges, **most of the experts (83%) did not miss any topic among the ones proposed per challenge**. Only few experts (17%) proposed additional topics. Namely, “AI enabled data management” for challenge 2, “Model Based Software Engineering” for challenge 3 and “Information integrity and sovereignty” for challenge 5.
- Experts were requested to prioritise the **draft set of recommendations** (presented as lessons learnt in [3]). The most important recommendation in their view is: “**Advanced Software Engineering research should be promoted**”, although the other recommendations were all ranked very close, which shows that all the recommendations were relevant for the experts. Experts were also requested to suggest additional recommendations. They added the following ones:
 - **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** is a "hot topic" in the short/medium term, specific recommendations in this regard should be highlighted.
 - Target awareness for the importance **of quality and security standards and compliance in the software domain** and promote actions focused on this.
 - Target awareness **for ethics and ownership in code programming**.
 - Promote actions focusing on **STEAM to increase the gender equality**.
 - **Quantum software development** should be aligned to the NISQ era, starting from **quantum knowledge**.

Questions 4-10 from the blocks 3-6 of the survey are related to the multi-factor methodology applied in the generation of the research and innovation roadmaps. They were assessed per challenge by the three experts. The results of the analysis of the methodology related questions can be summarised as follows:

- Most of the experts considered that it is important to know about **Digital Decade and Digital Compass** initiatives and related principles, and that this is having an impact on the challenges and topics identification. However, there is still some room to better align projects to policy initiatives and strategies, thus additional efforts are needed on this behalf.

- ❑ Most of the experts indicated that there is more than one **European project or infrastructures** related to the challenge and topic assessed. Few of them did not have knowledge on the existence of European projects and or infrastructures related with the assessed challenge and topics. This shows **the need of dissemination activities** to improve knowledge about European projects and or infrastructures related with a given challenge and topics to wider spread the European knowledge and current initiatives working on software related challenges.

The reviewers provided the following selection of initiatives regarding **best practices in the context of different challenges assessed**. Some already exist, while others are new actions practices proposed by the experts:

- Open-Source Initiative, Free Software Foundation, Eclipse community. In addition to those on SWForum.eu context there are useful approaches around OSS. *Challenge 1.*
 - Accompany companies in the migration to open software and have a space dedicated to sharing experiences. *Challenge 1.*
 - MyData initiative (<https://www.mydata.org/>) in Personal Data and Privacy. *Challenge 5.*
- ❑ Experts considered that **companies**, especially SMEs, **are not targeted enough** by the assessed challenges and topics.
- ❑ 88% of the experts consider that there is one or more **European projects** associated to the assessed challenge and topics that connect with relevant digital infrastructures, platforms and EDIHs. However, 22% consider that there is not enough knowledge about infrastructures, platforms and EDIHs or the assessed challenges do not connect with them.
- ❑ Most of the experts assessing **challenges from 1 to 4**, consider that there are European projects related with the assessed challenge and topics that **cross-fertilise** with others in view of generating added value for industry between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. For **challenges 5 and 6**, most of experts consider that **there is no cross-fertilisation** between relevant projects for the assessed challenge and topics.

The experts were requested to rank the answers to the following questions:

- ❑ Challenges priorities (question 2).
- ❑ Challenge topics (question 3). In SWForum.eu roadmap version 2 [3] each challenge is decomposed in topics that are described in detail. In the survey, the main challenge and topics are detailed, and the reviewer is requested to rank the research topics by priority.
- ❑ Recommendations (question 11). In SWForum.eu roadmap version 2 [3] preliminary recommendations were presented as lessons learnt. These lessons learnt were presented to the experts, who ranked them, and this ranking was used to create the final recommendations presented in section 5.

Appendix B contains the reviewers ranking details in relation to the above questions (questions 2, 3 and 11).

3.2 SWForum.eu projects experts

This section contains the results of the survey answered by SWForum.eu projects. The following six SWForum.eu projects took part in the survey with one response per project:

- ❑ VeriDevOps
- ❑ VEDLIoT - Very Efficient Deep Learning in IoT
- ❑ MEDINA
- ❑ AI-SPRINT AI IN SECURE PRIVACY-PRESERV COMP CONT
- ❑ H2020 PHYSICS

 MORPHEMIC

The table below maps the SWForum.eu projects reviewers with challenge reviewed:

Table 1. Relationship of research challenges reviewed by research and innovation projects

Challenge reviewed	Number of SWForum.eu project
Challenge 1: Open-source software.	1
Challenge 2: Self-repairing and self-healing: Defect prediction and fault localization using artificial intelligence.	2
Challenge 3: Continuous software engineering.	1
Challenge 4: Requirements, architecture and development.	1
Challenge 5: Cybersecurity and privacy.	1
Challenge 6: Software Engineering for Quantum computing. Specific technology domains.	NONE ⁸

The analysis of the SWForum.eu projects results show the following results:

- All projects considered **relevant to create a European forum and a Software research community** covering software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure.
- The challenges ranked with the highest priority are:
 - **Challenge 1:** Open-source software.
 - **Challenge 2:** Self-repairing and self-healing: Defect prediction and fault localization using artificial intelligence.
 - **Challenge 3 and 5** were ranked next with similar average priorities.
- Reviewers missed the following Challenges:
 - Cover the full design space from transistor to application using a codesign methodology.
 - **Real-time/Near-real-time systems**, performance management, system runtime adaptation.
 - **Low code platforms** Software modularity and reusability.
 - **Autonomic hyper distributed software systems** covering self-configuration and self-adaptation.
- No conclusions can be derived for the challenge topics ranking except for challenge 2 which was assessed by a relevant number of projects. The two topics identified with the highest priority for **challenge 2** are:
 - AI enabled execution configuration proposal and supervision.
 - AI enabled automatic evolution and adaptation through the Computing Continuum.
 - For challenge 1, 3 and 5, the ranking of topics is analysed in the section together with the challenge results of three experts. See further information in Appendix B – Rankings.

⁸ Quantum software engineering is an incipient research topic and no projects have been already funded under the targeted calls for the time when this survey was launched. Nevertheless, the Quantum challenge has been well covered through the other open consultation activities, targeting specific experts on the matter and organizing sessions focus on Quantum software engineering in the SWForum.eu workshops.

- ❑ The following additional topics were identified by Challenge:
 - **Challenge 2:** Reconfiguration (adaptation and evolution).
 - **Challenge 3:** Automated reconfiguration.
- ❑ The questions 4-10 from the blocks 3-6 were analysed together with TECNALIA experts' results to increase significance of the analysis. Additionally, challenge 2 experts did not agree in scoring these questions (4-10).
- ❑ SWForum.eu projects did not consider relevant to rank the recommendations. They were all equally relevant for them.

3.3 General Audience

As already indicated, a Slido poll was launched during the event in Brussels. The following results were gathered:

- ❑ *Q1: How do you assess the need to create a European forum and a Software research community covering software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure?*
88% of respondents considered **relevant to create a European forum and a Software research community** covering software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure.
- ❑ *Q2: Rank from the highest to the lowest priorities the six SWForum.eu research challenges from Figure 1.*
The results from the ranking from highest to lowest priority is as follows:
 1. Challenge 1: Open-source software.
 2. Challenge 3: Continuous software engineering.
 3. Challenge 5: Cybersecurity and privacy.
 4. Challenge 4: Requirements, architecture and development.
 5. Challenge 2: Self-repairing and self-healing: Defect prediction and fault localisation using artificial intelligence.
 6. Challenge 6: Software Engineering for Quantum computing. Specific technology domains
- ❑ *Q3: Which challenges do you envision in SW engineering for the next 5 years different from the previous ones?*
The following challenges were pointed out:
 - Reliability
 - Automation of software creation
 - AI-based software development
 - Trustworthiness of software due to an increasing use of generative AI
- ❑ *Q4: In your opinion, what are the most effective cybersecurity measures/concepts for the computing continuum?*
The measures/concepts identified are:
 - Strict software engineering principles, processes, and tools.
 - Deploying white boxes in the Cloud Edge IoT continuum to bring security, trusting chipsets and training like RISC-V.
- ❑ *Q5: Beyond support through investments, is there any regulatory and/or policy action that the Commission should undertake (new) or modify (existing)?*
The following suggestions were gathered:
 - Active policies for the incorporation of women to the IT workforce.
 - Have part of a project budget act as a seed capital for strengthening after-project continuation of development of the more promising project outcomes.
 - Make openness (open HW/SW, open standards) mandatory for public funded projects (EU down to regions) and for solution providers.

4 Concluding remarks

SWForum.eu, has followed an ambitious workplan during its 33 months of implementation with a central goal (stated in the DoA) of **raising awareness and strengthening the competitiveness of the European Software Industry by facilitating a sustainable European forum of stakeholders**. *The forum shall represent scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators, and policymakers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. This forum is key to share assets, lessons learned, and policies to facilitate engagement in the elaboration of a set of research and innovation roadmaps for the Future Secure Digital Continuum.* To reach the overall project goal, four specific objectives have guided the implementation:

- ❑ EU **cross-fertilization** between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity .
- ❑ The **self-sustainable forum** of researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas, as a living forum as well as a Fellowship programme, an online platform and a coordinated work to create research and innovation roadmaps .
- ❑ **The visibility** of European-based software technology projects, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity, both in the research and in the market domain, at an international level e.g., by a taxonomy for the classification of projects, the EU project radar .
- ❑ The **competitiveness of European initiatives** through the definition of a methodological approach to the improvement of their MTRL, Mentoring, Technology Transfer & Best Practices guiding towards Policy Innovation .

This Deliverable presents in this chapter, the main concluding remarks resulting from the roadmapping exercise implemented in WP3. The strategic **research and innovation roadmaps** aim at increasing the competitiveness of the software industry in Europe as well as to ensure the EU's technology independence in software, contributing to the research agendas of Horizon Europe and Digital Europe. Three **iterations of the research and innovation roadmaps** have been implemented to reach the scope, as already explained:

- ❑ the **first iteration** (results presented under Deliverable 3.3.)
- ❑ the **second iteration** (results presented under Deliverable 3.4.)
- ❑ and the **third iteration** which results are described in this Deliverable, D3.5.

The **conclusions** summarise and integrate all the feedback received during the different consultation processes and thus, evolve and validate previous Deliverables. The SWForum.eu **concluding remarks** have been structured in **two different blocks**: first block includes four **general level conclusions** around the main project objectives (C1-C4), and in the second block **specific concluding remarks** resulting from the roadmapping exercise (C5-C8). These concluding remarks are linked to policy recommendations (see section 5) as well as suggestions for implementation in section 6. Both set of conclusions and recommendations have been defined considering the feedback from the different stakeholders received during the consultation activities.

4.1 C1: Software technology and related initiatives are fragmented across different domains and stakeholders.

Software technology and related initiatives form a broad, complex and horizontal research field resulting from its reach, boundaries, etc. which causes fragmentation across major stakeholders (including policy-making and regulatory institutions) in the European Union and at member states. Scientific advances in software technologies such as the irruption of Artificial Intelligent and Quantum Computing paradigms require deep integration between the results of the diverse research and innovation communities, as already anticipated in the proposal, and confirmed by

the research e.g., dependability, communications, mobility, test and verification, safety as well as a deep revision of SDLC and SOLC processes, tools and techniques. Many of these interactions have not occurred or have resulted into inadequate interactions and cross-fertilisation outside their domains. This also translates in a lack of connection to existing initiatives, platforms and infrastructures.

Main concluding remark related to objective 1, is that **fragmentation prevents cross-fertilisation and impacts between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity.**

4.2 C2. Software ecosystem is not well connected and integrated.

Linked to the previous conclusion C1, it is also challenging for the ecosystem to better connect researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas. As said, Software is pervasive and thus, it is impacting too many domains, competences, stakeholders and communities, which currently are not working in an integrated manner.

Nurturing a densely connected ecosystem of European software technology research and development communities will result in reduced fragmentation especially nowadays, when increased integration is needed in several dimensions to achieve better impacts.

An appropriate forum can support this objective 2 as e.g., the **self-sustainable forum** of researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas, supported by the SWForum.eu project together with coordinated work.

4.3 C3. Software research is incipient for some technologies.

Software research is incipient for some of the related technologies; maturity of technologies varies as explained in the document; therefore, **research needs to be supported and promoted to reach EU's technology** independence in software and to contribute to the research agendas of Horizon Europe and Digital Europe. Together with it, **more awareness, visibility and synergies** of the European-based software technology projects, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity both in the research and in the market domain at an international level is needed in line with SWForum.eu's objective 3.

4.4 C4. SMEs and industry are not reaching the adequate level of competitiveness resulting from European initiatives.

SMEs are the engine of the European industry, and this is truer than ever in software related industries, where innovation has consistently been spearheaded by the SMEs in areas ranging from machine vision to new DevOps lifecycle processes.

SWForum.eu has demonstrated that still, these technologies are not generating enough competitiveness in industry and in particular for SMEs. This is linked to the fact that industry players and employees don't have the right skills to deal with the challenges that these technologies arise. Measures and strategies to overcome this should be immediately put in place to gain competitiveness and make companies participant of these processes. On the other hand, in disruptive technologies as AI or Quantum computing, technological SMEs are playing a leading role at European level which is not reflected in their participation at European projects. The integration of this know how at European projects could boost the leading position of Europe in these areas.

4.5 C5. The SWForum.eu Methodology is appropriate for the roadmapping exercise.

A **multi factor and multi scoring methodology** has been defined to evaluate and propose research and innovation challenges and topics, which are under the umbrella of this

SWForum.eu CSA. The methodology consists of a **matrix** that includes the six **challenges**, selected to reach the vision and the **five factors/criteria** (represented in figure 9) defined to target the scope and impact of the project. These have been assessed by experts by means of a Likert type methodology, weighted and after assessed again in additional consultation rounds.

Figure 9. SWForum.eu Methodological factors/criteria.

The methodology is appropriate for the research conducted as well as for the roadmapping exercise implemented according to the experts. The consultation process reflects the following concluding remarks per factor.

- ❑ **Factor 1. Framework conditions.** It is important to consider the EU strategies such as Digital Decade and Digital Compass and respect principles, but also that there is still **some room for more and better alignment**.
- ❑ **Factor 2. Technology readiness.** On the one hand, there is **not enough knowledge** on European projects or infrastructures related to the challenge and topic assessed, on the other hand, experts that have knowledge in the field can identify few related initiatives. The same applies to Good/Best practices that overall, were not known with few exceptions⁹. According to the methodology applied, this allows to conclude that the **challenges are not technology ready** yet e.g., there are not enough research projects associated, not enough connection to existing infrastructures, not enough best practices, or not enough knowledge on those. This implies the **need of insisting in awareness and dissemination** activities to improve knowledge about European projects and or infrastructures related with a given challenge and topics, more research related to these ones as well as looking and supporting more best practices.
- ❑ **Factor 3. Competitiveness of EU industry and SMEs.** The technologies covered by the challenges **are not mature enough yet to strengthen the competitiveness of the EU software industry, companies, and SMEs.** SMEs are not targeted enough by the assessed challenges and topics.
- ❑ **Factor 4. Ecosystem development and interaction.** The **ecosystem is not mature enough and there is not enough impact and connections with the related infrastructures yet.** Similar to factor 2, there is a lack of knowledge about infrastructures, platforms and EDIHs regarding the assessed challenges as well as a lack of connections.
- ❑ **Factor 5. Cross- fertilisation for added value.** **There is not enough cross fertilisation yet, not enough added value is generated for industry.** Most of the experts identified some cross-fertilisation and added value for industry between the areas of software, digital

⁹ Challenge 1. Open-Source Initiative, Free Software Foundation, Eclipse community. In addition to those on SWForum.eu context there are useful approaches around OSS, accompany companies in the migration to open software and have a space dedicated to sharing experiences. Challenge 5. MyData initiative (<https://www.mydata.org/>) in Personal Data and Privacy.

infrastructures, and cybersecurity, although this is not the case for challenges 5 and 6. With regards to the potential of creating a European forum and a Software research community related to software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure, this has been agreed by all the experts consulted.

4.6 C6. The six research and innovation challenges in the context of software technologies, cybersecurity and digital infrastructures are relevant for future research.

This has been confirmed by all the experts that have participated in the consultation process. All these research and innovation challenges aim at reaching a common vision, build a “perfect” software system that is produced and operated at no cost. The research and innovation challenges are presented figure 2.

The challenge ranked with the highest priority of importance during the consultation process by all respondents is **challenge 1: Open-source software** while challenge 6 Software Engineering for Quantum computing is the one ranked last.

Experts also recommended some additional challenges to be taken into consideration such as:

- ▣ High Performance Computing
- ▣ Reuse of software
- ▣ Codesign: Cover the full design space from transistor to application using a codesign methodology.
- ▣ Real-time/Near-real-time systems, performance management, system runtime adaptation.
- ▣ Low code platforms Software modularity and reusability.
- ▣ Autonomic hyper distributed software systems covering self-configuration and self-adaptation.

Additionally, they anticipated some of the challenges that might have higher impact in the next 5 years such as:

- ▣ Reliability
- ▣ Automation of software creation
- ▣ AI-based software development
- ▣ Trustworthiness of software due to an increasing use of generative AI

Among the challenges of Figure 2, AI topics are spread across many of the challenges. Additionally, as underlined by some experts, AI impact in software development will increase at short-medium term. It might justify considering AI in software (SDLC and SOLC) as an explicit challenge instead of a topic of other challenges.

4.7 C7. The topics associated to the challenges are all relevant.

From the different research topics associated to the challenges presented to the experts most of them they did not miss any other relevant topic. Only few experts proposed additional ones. Namely, challenge 2 (reconfiguration adaptation and evolution, AI-enabled management), challenge 3 (Model Based Software Engineering, Automated reconfiguration) and for challenge 5 (Information integrity and sovereignty). No additional topics were identified for the other challenges.

With respect to the rankings of the topics for each of the challenges, the following are ranked from most to less relevance, following the consultation process:

- ▣ Challenge 1: OSS sustainability and interoperability with private software, Open-Source Software for Artificial Intelligence, Open-Source Hardware and Open-Source Processors.

- ❑ Challenge 2: AI enabled execution configuration proposal and supervision.
- ❑ Challenge 3: Optimized DevOps, Smart (re-)assurance.
- ❑ Challenge 5: New and advanced architectures, technologies and methodologies to protect sensitive data in computing continuum (from cloud data centers through fog nodes to end devices), A common European reference security framework (that will enable the possibility to automate security tests) and AI to Detect, prevent and respond to system failure and AI to Detect, prevent and respond to system failure.

However, the fast evolution of software technologies makes necessary to continuously alignment the challenges and topics to the changing needs. Special effort should be devoted when dealing with disruptive paradigms (i.e., Generative AI in Software Engineering as a new challenge or topic; the need of aligning the Quantum software development to the NISQ era).

4.8 C8. The challenges, topics and associated technologies present different levels of maturity.

Overall, as found out in D3.4, challenges 4 and 5 are mature ones; challenge 1 and 2 are intermediate regarding their maturity and challenges 3 and 6 are the less mature ones. This finding was already presented under Deliverable 3.4. After the open consultation phase the overall assessment of the challenges shows to be a valid conclusion as described below:

- ❑ **Challenge 1- Open-Source Software:** Framework conditions, both Digital Decade and Digital Compass are well known and are having an impact on the challenge, topic and subtopics. This challenge is the most aligned with the Framework Conditions of all the considered for the analysis. With respect to the ecosystem, it is true that there exists an ecosystem of Open-source developers, and this is inherent to the open-source concept and the peculiarity of the approach. Nevertheless, the autonomous and diverse characteristics of the ecosystem has ended up in a set of distributed communities that conform the ecosystem and that usually are not grouped under a formal common platform or initiative. With respect to the technology readiness and existence of best practices again, due to the nature of the movement, there is space to work on specific best practices or technology guides covering the whole stack from the physical level (i.e., open-source processors) to the upper layer (i.e., practices and guidelines for specific software technologies like AI, Quantum, Cloud Continuum).
- ❑ **Challenge 2- Self-repairing and self-healing.** Framework conditions, both Digital Decade and Digital Compass are well known and are having an impact on the challenge, topic and subtopics but not fully aligned yet. In the case of CH2, two factors have been assessed with lower value: F4. Ecosystem development and F5. Cross fertilization. In this case, both are related as specific hub and forums need to be developed in specific context of self-repairing software could be developed. The concept of cognitive software can be achieved through the incorporation of AI techniques into the SLDC and SOLC to provide advanced and intelligent capabilities to the software so that it can be more robust, fault tolerant and trustworthy.
- ❑ **Challenge 3- Continuous software engineering.** Framework conditions, both Digital Decade and Digital Compass are known and respected, but this is not having an impact on the challenge, topic, and subtopics, so it is not fully aligned yet with the Framework conditions. Continuous software engineering is a known discipline into which a lot of effort has been put in the last years. It includes Continuous Development, Continuous Integration, and other related practices that have already been incorporated in the industry. However, these practices need to be revised to be incorporated and adapted to new computing paradigms such as DevOps.

- Challenge 4- Requirements, Architecture, and development.** Framework conditions, both Digital Decade and Digital Compass are well-known and respected, but this is not having an impact on the challenge, topic, and subtopics, so it is not fully aligned yet with the Framework conditions. Similarly, to CH3, CH4 is a well-known Software Engineering discipline which is reflected in the high scores achieved for every factor. Nevertheless, and due to the increased complexity of the software systems, AI techniques can and should be investigated to be incorporated to the early phases of the SDLC, i.e., requirements elicitation, architecture definition and actual development. To this respect, incorporation of techniques and methods from the research to the industry and more concrete alignment with SMEs needs is needed.
- Challenge 5- Cybersecurity and Privacy.** Framework conditions, both Digital Decade and Digital Compass are well-known and respected, but this is not having an impact on the challenge, topic, and subtopics, yet there is not an impact on the challenge topics and subtopics. However, the score is close to achieving it. Although the values are low and there are no projects and or infrastructures under the umbrella of SWForum.eu related to the topics and subtopics nor Good Practices, this is the Challenge which shows better position regarding the technology readiness. Cross fertilization can be developed in the context of Cybersecurity as this topic is transversal to several domains and technologies and currently existing platforms are much more focused and could be extended to cross fertilization with other technologies such as AI or Quantum, as it has begun to happen with other technology topics such as secure data management or Cloud Computing cybersecurity.
- Challenge 6- Quantum software engineering.** Framework conditions, both Digital Decade and Digital Compass are not aligned enough yet with the Framework conditions. Although it is close to be well-known and respected, it is still not having an impact on the challenge, topic, and subtopics. From the point of view of the technology readiness, the challenge shows lack of knowledge on the existence of projects and or infrastructures under and no Best Practices available. This challenge is the one with lower marks in all the factors. This is to be expected as Quantum Computing is one of the most novel recognised cut edge technologies and therefore, the application of software engineering techniques.

The following figure shows the overall results.

Figure 10. SWForum.eu assessment of the identified challenges towards the selected factors.

Although at topic level the prioritisation process was not executed in the consultation activities, this exercise has been presented in the workshops where the roadmaps were discussed. As shown in figure 11 it can also be observed a great diversity at topic level in terms of their

maturity level towards the different factors, the green ones being the more mature ones and the orange ones less so.

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	F1.Framework conditions	F2.Technology readiness	F3.European competitiveness	F4.Ecosystem development	F5.Cross fertilization
CH1: OS	OS for Continuum Trusted OS, OS for advanced technologies, Sustainable OS OSHW	OS for Continuum, Sustainable OS, Trusted Os OSHW, OS for advanced technologies	Sustainable OS OSHW, OS for advanced technologies, OS for the Continuum, Trusted OS	OSHW, OS for advanced technologies, OS for the Continuum, Trusted OS, Sustainable OS	OSHW, OS for the Continuum, Trusted OS, Sustainable OS OS for advanced technologies
CH2: Self-healing	Cognitive Code Trustable Code Sustainable code				
CH3: CSE	Smart re-assurance Co-Engineering Optimized DevOps				
CH4:REQ & ARCH	AI augmented software development Engineering AI-Enabled Software Systems				
CH5: CYBER & Privacy	(Cloud) Secure Posture Management Next generation risk assessment Sensitive Data in the CC	(Cloud) Secure Posture Management Next generation risk assessment Sensitive Data in the CC	(Cloud) Secure Posture Management Next generation risk assessment Sensitive Data in the CC	(Cloud) Secure Posture Management Next generation risk assessment Sensitive Data in the CC	(Cloud) Secure Posture Management Next generation risk assessment Sensitive Data in the CC
CH6: Quantum	Quantum feasibility Quantum architecture Quantum interoperability				

Figure 11 Topics maturity with respect to the selected factors

5 Policy Recommendations

The following **10 recommendations** have been prepared taking into consideration the previous Deliverable (D3.4), where the research team suggested already **lessons learnt** from the process followed. Since D3.4 was submitted, the consultation process, has evolved and has allowed us to validate those lessons learnt, aggregate suggestions and provide a set of **10 policy recommendations** based on the learnings from the process. Each of the policy recommendation includes a general description as well as more specific ones linked and inspired on the specific conclusions and results from the SWForum.eu full process.

The preliminary set of recommendations has been shared during the consultation process to better understand the relevance of these, as well as how to prioritise them to suggest potential timing for implementation. All experts have suggested recommendation *2-Advanced Software Engineering research should be promoted* as the most relevant one now, although all the other recommendations were equally relevant too. Experts were also enquired on potential recommendations that might be missing which have also been added to this list.

5.1 R1. Software engineering concept delineation for EU cross-fertilisation and added value

Software is a horizontal discipline, that runs on top of a large variety of technologies and infrastructures, ranging from traditional cloud to edge/fog clouds HPC, Artificial Intelligence and soon, quantum computers. In addition, open-source software (OSS) is transversal to all of them being "Think Open" the new mindset change promoted by the European Commission around OSS and now being extended to Open-Source Hardware (OSH). Software opens significant challenges in terms of security and privacy, leading to the need for guaranteeing trustworthiness, self-adaptation, optimisation of behaviour and the like. It is more and more pervasive and should rely into other technologies (e.g., cybersecurity, AI) to solve complex problems. SDLC and SOLC engineering processes, methods and practices should also be adapted and updated to fit the new emerging software paradigms (e.g., IA, Quantum computing, trustworthiness in complex supply chains, computing limited resources).

Software-related technologies have become so interwoven with the surrounding technologies – Internet of Things, seamless and secure cloud-based mobility, energy-efficient embedded systems, advanced AI, and Big Data algorithms – that cross-domain fertilisation has become a must for progress and leadership. But, as concluded (see C1, C5), many of these interactions have not occurred or have resulted into inadequate interactions and cross-fertilisation outside their domains.

Software engineering is usually understood as programming, but it involves a much broader concept. The main aim of software engineering is to develop reliable models and techniques for producing high quality software in an efficient way, from theory to practice. Therefore, software engineering needs to evolve as new paradigms (computing, social, environmental, technological) arises.

To make better use of connections, avoid fragmentation, promote cross fertilisation among different technologies and policy areas regarding software and specially software engineering **a delineation of the software engineering is recommended**, intending to delimit the concept to better known, track and anticipate opportunities and impacts for interaction and higher added value at regional, national and EU level as well as improved **cross-fertilisation** between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity.

The consultation work implemented in the project together with experts has also highlighted this problem, as for the difficulties to assess the challenges, topics and impacts. Expert's opinions

are that there is a cross fertilisation among initiatives of the different challenges except for challenges 5 and 6, where most of experts consider that there is no cross-fertilisation between relevant projects for the assessed challenge and topics (see C5). The **6 research and innovation challenges proposed** in SWForum.eu, have been confirmed, by all the experts that have participated in the consultation process, **as very relevant for future research in the context of software technologies, cybersecurity and digital infrastructures** (see C6). Therefore, we recommend using **the six challenges and associated topics for a better software engineering delineation**. Together with the delineation of the concept, another suggestion is to **cluster projects and actions around the challenges**. This will allow better cross fertilisation as well as monitoring.

However, these challenges and topics are not static. They should be continuously monitored and adjusted considering the fast evolvement of software technologies in particular when dealing with disruptive paradigms such as AI and quantum computing but also the most recent contributions of Generative AI or limited resources form the edge, for instance. Additionally, a higher involvement of EU network experts would be required to improve the consultation process as well as to test solutions before investing being also a source of knowledge to feed strategies and programmes.

5.2 R2: Consider Advanced Software Engineering as a research discipline supported by a research forum and community

Nowadays software is pervasive because specific software is needed in almost every industry, in every business, and for every function. Therefore, software is seen as a commodity to many other domains. Software can help the technological evolution in many other disciplines as a supporting mean to improve and create advance research. This does not preclude the importance of researching in the domain of software engineering itself.

SWForum.eu has permitted to create a vision on future research and innovation for software engineering, by means of **6 challenges** and associated topics. Even though the research work has demonstrated that all the challenges are valid and relevant, **overall, they are not technology ready yet and more research is needed** (see C3, C5). This has been concluded by SwForum.eu and shared with experts during the consultation process: e.g., associated technologies are not well-known, there are not enough software EU research projects, these projects don't reach enough SMEs, they don't connect with relevant existing infrastructures, etc. This is specially the case for Quantum software engineering (challenge 6), which values are the lowest followed by and Open-source software (challenge 1) Self-repairing and self-healing (challenge 2).

As any other scientific domain, research on software engineering as an **EU research discipline needs to be promoted** to tackle future challenges and better contribute to the EU Strategies and policy frameworks specially to reach EU's technology independence in software and to contribute to the research agendas of Horizon Europe and Digital Europe (see C3). This involves defining an own work programme, agenda, etc. **specific to Software Engineering discipline**, working together with industry to better understand their needs as well as government and the software engineering community. A specific research Work programme will permit to continue with the research aligned with the EU and national policy frameworks, that now are defragmented (see C1, C7, C8) and in line with the maturity of the technologies associated to the challenges and topics. Having a specific programme addressing the specific needs for software technologies, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity around the **topic of advance software engineering** will help to define a more aligned strategy at European and national level as well as a greater involvement of the network in the definition of these strategies (at regional, national or European level).

Support a software **research community** has been strongly recommended by all the consulted experts as well as a **self-sustainable living forum** of researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas covering “*software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure*”. This Forum can be participated by different stakeholders and e.g., EDIHs, Industry Associations, National and International Standards Associations, and Academia. The Forum should be the platform that can support in the strategy to follow, the identification of the challenges, topics, etc. This will also permit to connect researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas (see C2, C5) avoiding fragmentation. Such a community needs to be rolled out through specific support actions and programmes providing funding to support it.

Linked to the previous conclusion, it is also challenging for the ecosystem to better connect researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas. Nurturing a densely connected ecosystem of European software technology research and development communities is needed to avoid fragmentation when increased integration is needed in several dimensions to achieve better impacts. An appropriate Forum can support this objective.

Here are a preliminary suggestion of instruments to better target the recommendations:

- ❑ **High mature research and innovation challenges:** for most mature and well aligned challenges (challenge 4-Requirements, architecture and development and challenge 5-Cyber security and privacy) more applied research is recommended by means of instruments boosting the market readiness level of proven technologies, such as the current Innovation Actions or similar programmes.
- ❑ **Partially mature research and innovation challenges.** For those challenges that are partially mature (challenge 1: Open-Source Software and challenge 2: Self-repairing and self-healing software) while some areas are well covered, actions towards increasing the maturity on the other factors need to be taken. As an example, in the Open-Source arena, whereas open-source software is widely supported and adopted paradigm, open-source hardware (i.e., open-source processors and RISC-V, cloud computing open-source stack, open-source computing continuum, etc.) needs to be fostered. Here more domain specific research and basic research needs to be promoted.
- ❑ **Low mature research and innovation challenges.** The challenges under this category, are the ones which need larger development. As expected, these challenges cover cutting edge technologies (such as challenge 6-Quantum Software Engineering) or software related subjects highly impacted by the technologies paradigm shift. This is the case of challenge 3-Continuous Software Engineering, which needs to be adapted to the upcoming technologies, such as DevOps for AI systems, Software Engineering Techniques for the computing continuum, or new CI/CD approaches covering the metaverse needs. For these more horizontal challenges specific instruments such as Coordination and Support Action (CSA) could be already recommended or other initiatives fostering the cross fertilization and the creation of networks around these topics.

5.3 R3: Targeted awareness for software, considering businesses needs

Software, as already mentioned, is a horizontal discipline that runs on top of a large variety of infrastructures and is becoming increasingly pervasive posing the need to be combined with others. This makes this discipline very challenging for researchers as well as for companies. As complexity increases, software related projects are more challenging for companies as for time constraints, lack of skilled workers, lack of resources and budget for the development processes, for the definition of the project’s requirements, for the complexity of systems and legal

frameworks, for security issues at organisational and technical level, as well as for the communication among company developers and customers, for instance.

But on the contrary, the right use of software in combination with other technologies can bring important added value for companies. Therefore, **targeted awareness campaigns** are needed to show the benefits that especially European-based software technology projects can bring. Targeted awareness and dissemination actions should also focus on actions such as, creating confidence and trust on these technologies as well as quality, security standards, compliance, ethics, and ownership in code programming. Awareness and dissemination related activities should also target related European projects and or infrastructures to enhance their visibility and connectivity (see C1, C3, C5) of the opportunities and activities of the EU-software related projects under the umbrella of the CSA and potentially replicated for other similar projects.

SWForum.eu has managed to **reach the community** by means of the **self-sustainable forum** (see R3) where researchers and practitioners in software technologies and related areas connect, cooperate and work together to better understand software challenges and come with solutions. This platform needs to be promoted as a means of awareness raising as well as, a precondition to support the better understanding of these challenges by the society in general.

5.4 R4: Identification and promotion of Inspiring stories for better trust

The identification and promotion of good practices and success stories are good means for creating trust and better knowledge on these technologies facilitated by real and successful examples. Software Industry, businesses and in particular SMEs, need to see the benefits and the added value of digital transformation by means of these stories that can be of inspiration for others.

Good practices are recommended to be collected broadly showcasing the impacts of the software related technologies in business operations. Presenting software technologies as way to improve the company's productivity and competitiveness. The SWForum.eu related projects can contribute to identify and share good practices of SDLC and SOLC e.g., the Open-Source Initiative, Free Software Foundation, Eclipse community. The consultation process has demonstrated that best practices on the challenges defined to be further promoted (see C5).

5.5 R5: Shared strategy and policy alignment for software including legal frameworks, quality, security standards and compliance

The Commission and the member states are already working together on a **shared strategy for digital transformation including** software, nevertheless these initiatives can be further reinforced in the sake of advanced competitiveness and sovereignty in the area. Software is a horizontal discipline **connected to many policy areas**, as highlighted in the Digital Decade e.g., computing continuum, artificial intelligence, data governance, data spaces, cybersecurity as well as cutting-edge technologies for industry such as Quantum Computing. Cooperation in **legal and certification frameworks** is also very relevant in the field of software for better and faster software development and integration of the different frameworks that exist now.

Synergies between Horizon Europe and other EU/national initiatives could still be improved to provide a more holistic support to respond to the SMEs demand regarding new technologies in the field of software.

The specific analysis implemented in the project, including the scoring Methodology shows that there is a **lack of alignment of the challenges defined in the project with the EU Framework**

conditions considered , (Digital Decade and Digital Compass¹⁰). Open-source software (Challenge 1) is the most aligned challenge with the Framework Conditions together with Self-repairing and self-healing (Challenge 2) whereas Quantum software engineering (Challenge 6) is the less aligned. This is an indication of the need to better align software as a technology with policy and strategy for better results in some key areas that have further space for development. This also applies to Quantum software development that need better alignment according to the experts' feedback to the NISQ era, starting from quantum knowledge.

5.6 R6: Skills development programmes & training activities for software need to be promoted

Finding qualified skills and reskilling of employees is one of the most important challenges for companies regarding digital transformation, and this is not an exception for companies dealing with software. There is not only a lack of qualified workers but also a high cost of hiring qualified people in this specific field.

Software engineering is implemented by many employees and people with interdisciplinary skills, but not specially focusing on software by its nature. An understanding of what is needed by companies is needed to define the training needs as well as the corresponding training programmes that fit the demand.

Although the European Commission is committed to tackle the digital skills gap by supporting projects and strategies to improve the level of digital skills in Europe, and many other initiatives are also in place at national and regional level, this should be reinforced.

Initiatives such as the European **Digital Skills and Jobs Platform**¹¹ launched under the Connecting Europe Facility Programme should be promoted for SMEs. It offers information and resources on digital skills, as well as training and funding opportunities. Specific programmes for advanced software engineering experts need to be developed to train the professionals of the future, towards European digital sovereignty and autonomy. To this end, programmes on advanced and cutting-edge technologies need to be incorporated and traditional software engineering programmes need to be renewed with advanced paradigms (i.e., software engineering for advanced technologies (AI, Quantum, etc), self-repairing software, Quantum DevOps, development of open-source technologies, IAOps, etc.).

Standardisation is also needed regarding digital qualifications and training in this field as currently there are only a few official programmes covering these aspects in Software Engineering.

The project also contributes to reduce the skills gap by means of a **Fellowship programme**. One of the main aims of the fellowship programme is the incorporation of young researchers into the SWForum.eu community to dynamize and create discussion around the selected topics relevant to software technologies.

5.7 R7: Policy actions in the field should target the Competitiveness of EU industry and SMEs

The Competitiveness for EU industry has been assessed based on the influence of the technologies to strengthen the competitiveness of the European Software Industry - including the underlying digital infrastructures together with the need of security mechanisms. Overall,

¹⁰ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_en

¹¹ [Digital skills and jobs | Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_en)

the six challenges analysed in SWForum.eu show that the companies involved on the associated projects under the umbrella of SWForum.eu are big companies, although projects might target SMEs and large companies for their impacts and results. In the case of Quantum software engineering (challenge 6) big companies are targeted on the associated projects under the umbrella of SWForum.eu.

Therefore, these technologies are not yet involving SMEs or specially addressing SMEs when looking for impacts or projects. This result is also related to the fact that technologies are not mature/ready enough as indicated under previous recommendation (see C4, C5).

SWForum.eu research has demonstrated that companies and **especially SMEs, can be better targeted by the assessed challenges and topics through existing or new networks (e.g., EDHIs, TEFs, associations)**, and therefore, better knowledge of companies needs is a preliminary step to determinate the actions needed.

5.8 R8: Improved connections of existing digital infrastructures, platforms, and other relevant initiatives

The software ecosystem is understood as the set of stakeholders e.g., scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators, policy makers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity, etc. cooperating and representing the industry, the government, the universities as well as citizens. The connections and cooperation between the software-related ecosystem, making use of available digital infrastructures that can support businesses to increase their competitiveness is very important.

SWForum.eu has demonstrated that research communities and infrastructures, platforms, etc are not connected enough, resulting probably from the lack of awareness but also from the fragmentation at EU, national and regional levels (see C1, C2, C4, C6).

Associations, European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), TEFs (Testing and Experimentation Facilities), etc. should be aware of the available infrastructures, how to use them, etc. to facilitate access to them for all organisations and SMEs. Connections to EDIHs and TEFs are highly relevant as they are both a priority to implement the Digital Europe Programme. EDIHs and TEFs support companies to respond to the digital challenges and become more competitive offering services as a one-stop-shop and target digital technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity and High-performance computing, but also provide support to create and sustain an innovation ecosystem as well as networking for companies. On top of this EDIHs, the European Networks and platforms are also key to support connections and knowledge in this ecosystem such as **ECSSO**- European Cyber Security Organisation and **ADRA**- AI Data Robotics Partnerships as well as relevant Digital infrastructures.

Connections and cooperation with these initiatives will support in the **cross-fertilisation** between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity as well as support and respond to companies' demand.

Overall, for the other challenges the values of the scoring are very low, so that there is not probably enough knowledge on the existence of relevant digital infrastructures, platforms and EDIHs to assess the Challenge, topic/subtopic, the ecosystem is not ready yet and in conclusion there is not enough potentiality to create a self-sustainable forum.

It is recommended to promote the creation of interoperable and secure European platforms to address software development during SDLC as well as SOLC in any of the relevant technology domains (i.e., IoT, Smart cities, Cloud and Edge computing). In parallel appropriate

methodologies, techniques, tools, and certifications should be put in place as soon as new needs from the software network and ecosystem arise (i.e., Software Engineering for Quantum Computing).

5.9 R9: SWForum.eu as an inspiring methodology for other projects

SWForum.eu methodology has proven to be an adequate **multi factor and multi scoring methodology** to identify research and innovation challenges and assess early-stage technologies. The Methodology includes research work, field work by means of consultation to experts in different rounds and validation as feedback loops for the methodology. This methodology can be of use for other similar projects and processes.

We consider that the proposed challenges, topics per challenge and recommendations provided in the version 2 roadmap are a good foundation to strengthen the research domain on “*Software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure*”. This idea is reinforced by the fact that most reviewers considered that *Advanced Software Engineering research should be promoted*.

5.10 R10: Promote actions focus on STEAM to increase the gender equality

The recent Commission working document¹² confirms that Europe has a **strong gender imbalance and shortage of digital experts and ICT specialist** to develop cutting-edge technologies. ICT specialists are employed across all sectors of the economy and that the gender gap is particularly high in some of the fastest-growing and highest-paid jobs of the future, like computer science and engineering. The digitalisation of the economy provides greater opportunities for the inclusion of women in the labour market, as women make up most tertiary education.

The Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027 sets out a long-term approach and vision for high quality, inclusive and accessible digital education in Europe by means of two strategic priorities: Fostering the development of a high-performing digital education ecosystem and enhancing digital skills and competences for the digital transformation.

She Figures2021¹³, highlights that both at European and at country level, although the number of women Doctoral graduates has continued to grow gradually, the **horizontal gender segregation persists** in certain fields of education. Women Doctoral graduates were over-represented in the field of Education and under-represented in the fields of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction. Little progress towards increasing women’s representation among Doctoral graduates in Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) has been observed, especially because with age at higher levels of education, girls tend to move away from some STEM and ICT¹⁴.

In the EU labour market, women in ICT careers are below 2% of women's total share. STEM fields and the digital sector (e.g., digital technologies, CS, IT, ICT, AI, cybersecurity) are among the employment domains where gender bias prevails¹⁵.

¹² [deap-swd-digital-skills-180423_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

¹³ https://cfm.ehu.es/view/files/she_figures_2021.pdf

¹⁴ Eurostat (2020)(europa.eu): - Tertiary education statistics

¹⁵ [Education and employment of women in science, technology and the digital economy, including AI and its influence on gender equality \(europa.eu\)](#)

Specific measures should be promoted focusing on STEAM to support gender equality as well as active policies and strategies to incorporate women to the ICT workforce. This is especially needed regarding Information and Communication Technologies as gender segregation has negative impacts, especially in the context of the rapid transformation and digitalisation of the economy.

6 Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable has presented the third and final version of SWForum.eu research and innovation roadmaps on software technologies, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructures. In this final version the challenges and topics defined in research and innovations roadmaps v2 have been assessed with the community to complement them and extract the policy related recommendations to address the roadmap.

Although it is difficult to envision on future research challenges in the timeframe of 5 to 10 years from now, SWForum.eu proposes a set of 10 recommendations, some of them in the long term, others in the short term (see Table 2). This is the case of R2, as this was already suggested by experts.

Table 2. Timing suggested to address the proposed recommendations

List of Recommendations	Timing*
R1. Software engineering concept delineation for EU cross-fertilisation and added value	Short-medium
R2: Consider Advanced Software Engineering as a research discipline supported by a research forum and community	Short
R3: Targeted awareness for software, considering businesses needs	Short
R4: Identification and promotion of Inspiring stories for better trust	Short-medium
R5: Shared strategy and policy alignment for software including legal frameworks, quality, security standards and compliance	Short-medium
R6: Skills development programmes & training activities for software need to be promoted	Short-medium
R7: Policy actions in the field should target the Competitiveness of EU industry & SMEs.	Short
R8: Improved connections of existing digital infrastructures, platforms and other relevant initiatives	Short
R9: SWForum.eu as an inspiring methodology for other projects	Medium
R10. Promote actions focus on STEAM to increase the gender equality	Short

*We define short term as less than 5 years, medium terms between 5-10 years, and long-term more than 10 years.

On top of this, experts have also anticipated some short-term **additional challenges** such as Reliability Automation of software creation and AI-based software development as well as specific measures/concepts to be implemented such as the promotion of strict software engineering principles, processes, and tools and deploying white boxes in the Cloud Edge IoT continuum to bring security, trusting chipsets and training like RISC-V.

Also, from the analysis performed on the research challenges and topics in figure 11, different priority levels for the actions to be implemented for each of the identified topics can be proposed, in the different dimensions depending on their maturity level towards the different factors. To this extent different timing on the actions are suggested to implement for the different challenges and topics towards the different factors (See figure 12).

Figure 12. Research and Innovation topics roadmap organized per factor

These challenges and topics need to be closely monitored and the research domains need to be continuously adapted. SWForum.eu will keep the update and adaptation of such research lines through the participation on future initiatives and works.

7 References

- [1] SWForum.eu Consortium, «D3.3- Software Forum Research Roadmap v1,» 2021.
- [2] TECNALIA, «D3.4- Software Forum Research Roadmap v2,» 2022.
- [3] SWForum Project, «D4.4-MTRL methodology and assessments v1,» 2022.

APPENDIX A: Open Consultation surveys

In these appendixes the questions from the different surveys implemented are included.

Experts survey & projects survey

Block 0: Identification (only for the projects)

- Project Acronym and Name:
- Project web page URL:

Block 1: Introduction

- How do you assess the need to create a European forum and a Software research community covering software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure?

Block 2: Research & Innovation Challenges

- How important do you consider the following Research and Innovation challenges in the field of software technology, cybersecurity and digital infrastructure? Can you prioritise?
- Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant two?
- Select the challenge in which you are an expert (select only one):
 - Challenge 1. Open-source software.
 - Which of the following topics are more relevant for Challenge 1? please prioritise
 - Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant 2?
 - Challenge 2. Self-repairing and self-healing: Defect prediction and fault localization using artificial intelligence.
 - Which of the following topics are more relevant for Challenge 2? please prioritise
 - Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant 2?
 - Challenge 3. Continuous software engineering.
 - Which of the following topics are more relevant for Challenge 3? please prioritise
 - Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant 2?
 - Challenge 4. Requirements, architecture and development.
 - Which of the following topics are more relevant for Challenge 4? please prioritise topics in each block: AI-Augmented Software Development, AI-Enabled Software Systems.
 - Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant 2?
 - Challenge 5. Cybersecurity and privacy
 - Which of the following topics are more relevant for Challenge 5? please prioritise
 - Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant 2?
 - Challenge 6. Software Engineering for Quantum computing.
 - Which of the following topics are more relevant for Challenge 5? please prioritise
 - Do you miss any challenge? If so, please list the most relevant 2?

Block 3. Challenge Alignment to framework conditions

- How do you assess the challenge in relation to the Digital Decade?
- How do you assess the challenge in relation to the Digital Compass?

Block 4. Technology Readiness

- Are there European Research and Innovation projects and relevant infrastructures in relation to the challenge and topics?

- ❑ In your opinion are there best practices on the challenge topics available to the Software community i.e. white papers, strategic research and innovation agendas, etc.? If yes, can you specify?

Block 5. Competitiveness of EU industry & SMEs

- ❑ Are there European companies, in particular SMEs, working on or targeted by the challenge topics in the European Research and Innovation projects?

Block 6. Ecosystem development and interaction: EDIHs, partnerships and Digital infrastructures

- ❑ In your opinion is the challenge connected to relevant infrastructures, networks, European Digital Innovation Hubs, etc.?

Block 7. Cross fertilisation for added value

- ❑ In your opinion are current European Research and Innovation projects related to the challenge collaborating with others and generating added-value synergies for the industry?
- ❑ If you select the second option, can you please describe any cross-fertilization example?

Block 8: Recommendations

- ❑ Can you prioritise the following recommendations? They apply to challenges 1 to 6.
- ❑ You can add new recommendations here:

General audience slido

- ❑ How do you assess the need to create a European forum and a Software research community covering software technology, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure?
- ❑ How important do you consider the following Research and innovation challenges in the field of SW technology, cybersecurity and digital infrastructure? Can you prioritise?
- ❑ Which challenges do you envision in SW engineering for the next 5 years different from the previous ones?
- ❑ Beyond support through investments, is there any regulatory and/or policy action that the Commission should undertake (new) or modify (existing)?

APPENDIX B: Rankings of challenges, topics and recommendations

Ranking from the projects

Challenges ranking

Challenges ranking from the projects	PR1	PR2	PR3	PR4	PR5	PR6
Challenge 1: Open-source software.;	1	3	4	1	1	6
Challenge 2: Self-repairing and self-healing: Defect prediction and fault localization using artificial intelligence.;	4	2	1	2	3	4
Challenge 3: Continuous software engineering.;	5	4	3	3	2	2
Challenge 4: Requirements, architecture and development.;	2	6	5	4	4	1
Challenge 5: Cybersecurity and privacy.;	3	1	2	5	5	3
Challenge 6: Software Engineering for Quantum computing. Specific technology domains.	6	5	6	6	6	5

Concluding remarks ranking

Concluding remarks	PR1	PR2	PR3	PR4	PR5	PR6
Promote the visibility of digital infrastructures, platforms and EDIHs	5	7	5	1	7	6
Skills development programmes & training activities for software need to be promoted	3	5	1	2	6	3
Advanced Software Engineering related research should be promoted	9	1	6	3	1	1
Identification and promotion of good practices	4	4	2	4	4	7
Policy alignment for software needs to be fostered	6	8	3	5	5	4
Technology is not ready yet regarding software technologies. More research is needed	7	2	7	6	2	2
Targeted awareness for software landscape and use for businesses	2	6	4	7	3	5
Competitiveness of EU industry & SMEs should be better targeted	1	3	8	8	8	8

Topics ranking

Challenge 1 topics	PR5
Open-Source Software for Artificial Intelligence	4
Open-Source Hardware and Open-Source Processors	3
Open-Source Software Quantum Computing	5
OSS sustainability and interoperability with private software	2
Trusted and secure Open-Source Software and Open-Source Hardware	6
Open-Source for the Computing Continuum	1

Challenge 2 topics	PR1	PR3
AI enabled code repair, code error detections, predictions and solution proposals	4	3
AI enabled execution configuration proposal and supervision	1	2
AI enabled cybersecurity threats detection	3	4
AI enabled automatic evolution and adaptation through the Computing Continuum	2	1

Challenge 3 topics	PR4
Smart (re-)assurance	4
Co-engineering	3
Levering feedback and runtime information	2
Optimized DevOps	1

Challenge 4 topics	PR6
AI-Augmented Software Development	
Development of scalable, secure and private safe, performant and standardised reference architectures & compliant platforms at European&International level (technology and domain specific e.g. IoT platforms).;	4
NLP and heuristics apply to requirements engineering & conceptual models.;	1
Scale auto code generation and repair.;	6
Collect evidence demonstrating developers' acceptance and efficacy of AI assistance.;	7
Automate design, evolution, and analysis tools.;	2
Identify new forms of evidence of quality.;	8
Re-envisioned software development lifecycle.;	3
Communication and performance related issues in loosely coupled architectures & how to migrate from traditional to loosely coupled architectures.	5
AI-Enabled Software Systems	
Design and analysis methods for AI-enabled system.	4
Testing practices for AI-enabled systems.	5
AI-enabled system specification methods	1
Data management in support of AI-enabled systems	2
Uncertainty management methods. There need to be techniques to model, analyse, and design for uncertainty	6
Continuous monitoring and sustainment. AI-systems need to be effectively monitored, self-healed, evolved, and sustained.	3

Challenge 5 topics	PR2
AI to Detect, prevent and respond to system failure	12
Continuous analysis of 3rd party libraries to detect security & privacy issues.	10
Tools to assess security risk assessment in containerised clouds.	4
Security in APPs and services (Sw Engineering in SDLC and OT - APPs in operation.	3
(Cloud) Secure Posture Management.	5

Development kit for the automatization of IaC-Infrastructure as Code secure solutions for cloud paradigms (i.e., containers) & associated modelling language (e.g., DOML for Piacere project).	11
Secure Adaptive edge/cloud compute & network continuum over a heterogeneous sparse edge infrastructure to support nextgen applications.	13
A common European reference security framework (that will enable the possibility to automate security tests).	1
Automatically express and manage security requirements in an effective and unambiguous way	2
Task allocation and authorization constraints.	9
New and advanced architectures, technologies and methodologies to protect sensitive data in computing continuum (from cloud data centers through fog nodes to end devices).	6
Vulnerability free code correctors.	8
Safety verification tools to assess safety in an automatic or semi-automatic way.	7

Ranking from the Experts

Challenges ranking

Challenges ranking from the Experts	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16	R17	R18
Challenge 1	4	1	1	1	1	1	5	5	4	2	1	1	5	4	5	1	3	4
Challenge 2	5	5	4	3	2	3	2	3	1	5	2	4	4	5	3	2	4	3
Challenge 3	2	3	2	2	3	2	1	4	3	4	3	2	2	2	4	3	5	2
Challenge 4	6	4	3	4	6	4	3	1	5	1	4	3	1	1	1	4	6	1
Challenge 5	1	2	5	5	4	5	4	2	2	3	5	5	3	3	2	5	1	5
Challenge 6	3	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	2	6

Concluding remarks ranking

Concluding remarks ranking from the Experts	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16	R17	R18
Promote the visibility of digital infrastructures, platforms and EDIHs	2	1	3	5	7	7	4	6	2	3	1	1	6	7	5	4	2	7
Skills development programmes & training activities for software need to be promoted	7	4	6	4	4	3	3	8	5	4	2	2	8	2	2	3	1	4
Advanced Software Engineering related research should be promoted	3	7	7	3	5	1	1	2	4	5	3	3	2	3	6	7	5	2
Identification and promotion of good practices	5	3	1	8	2	8	6	5	3	1	4	4	1	4	3	6	4	5
Policy alignment for software needs to be fostered	1	6	5	7	1	4	8	4	1	6	5	5	3	6	1	1	8	6

Technology is not ready yet regarding software technologies. More research is needed	8	8	4	1	6	2	5	1	8	8	6	6	7	1	4	5	3	1
Targeted awareness for software landscape and use for businesses	4	2	2	2	3	6	2	7	7	7	7	7	4	5	8	2	6	3
Competitiveness of EU industry & SMEs should be better targeted	6	5	8	6	8	5	7	3	6	2	8	8	5	8	7	8	7	8

Topics ranking

Challenge 1 - Topics	R1	R2	R3
Open-Source Software for Artificial Intelligence	5	1	1
Open-Source Hardware and Open-Source Processors	2	3	3
Open-Source Software Quantum Computing	3	5	5
OSS sustainability and interoperability with private software	4	2	2
Trusted and secure Open-Source Software and Open-Source Hardware	1	4	4
Open-Source for the Computing Continuum	6	6	6

Challenge 2 Topics	R4	R5	R6	PR	PR
AI enabled code repair, code error detections, predictions and solution proposals	1	4	2	4	3
AI enabled execution configuration proposal and supervision	2	3	1	1	2
AI enabled cybersecurity threats detection	3	2	4	3	4
AI enabled automatic evolution and adaptation through the Computing Continuum	4	1	3	2	1

Challenge 3 Topics	R7	R8	R9	PR
Smart (re-)assurance	2	4	1	4
Co-engineering	3	2	3	3
Levering feedback and runtime information	4	3	4	2
Optimized DevOps	1	1	2	1

Challenges 4 Topics	R10	R11	R12	PR
AI-Augmented Software Development				
Development of scalable, secure and private safe, performant and standardarised reference architectures & compliant platforms at European&International level (technology and domain specific e.g. IoT platforms).;	1	1	1	4
NLP and heuristics apply to requirements engineering & conceptual models.;	3	2	2	1
Scale auto code generation and repair.;	4	3	3	6
Collect evidence demonstrating developers' acceptance and efficacy of AI assistance.;	7	4	4	7
Automate design, evolution, and analysis tools.;	2	5	5	2
Identify new forms of evidence of quality.;	6	6	6	8
Re-envisioned software development lifecycle.;	5	7	7	3
Communication and performance related issues in loosely coupled architectures & how to migrate from traditional to loosely coupled architectures.	8	8	8	5

Challenges 4 Topics	R10	R11	R12	PR
AI-Enabled Software Systems				
Design and analysis methods for AI-enabled system.	2	1	1	4
Testing practices for AI-enabled systems.	4	2	2	5
AI-enabled system specification methods	1	3	3	1
Data management in support of AI-enabled systems	3	4	4	2
Uncertainty management methods. There need to be techniques to model, analyse, and design for uncertainty	6	5	5	6
Continuous monitoring and sustainment. AI-systems need to be effectively monitored, self-healed, evolved, and sustained.	5	6	6	3

Challenge 5 topics	R13	R14	R15	PR
AI to Detect, prevent and respond to system failure	2	3	1	12
Continuous analysis of 3rd party libraries to detect security & privacy issues.	5	6	10	10
Tools to assess security risk assessment in containerised clouds.	7	9	9	4
Security in APPs and services (Sw Engineering in SDLC and OT - APPs in operation.	3	7	8	3

(Cloud) Secure Posture Management.	11	10	4	5
Development kit for the automatization of IaC-Infrastructure as Code secure solutions for cloud paradigms (i.e., containers) & associated modelling language (e.g., DOML for Piacere project).	9	12	6	11
Secure Adaptive edge/cloud compute & network continuum over a heterogeneous sparse edge infrastructure to support nextgen applications.	4	5	11	13
A common European reference security framework (that will enable the possibility to automate security tests).	12	1	3	1
Automatically express and manage security requirements in an effective and unambiguous way	13	2	5	2
Task allocation and authorization constraints.	10	13	12	9
New and advanced architectures, technologies and methodologies to protect sensitive data in computing continuum (from cloud data centers through fog nodes to end devices).	1	4	2	6
Vulnerability free code correctors.	6	11	7	8
Safety verification tools to assess safety in an automatic or semi-automatic way.	8	8	13	7

Challenge 6 topics	R16	R17	R18
Quantum software viability studies	1	3	1
Quantum software architecture	3	4	2
Quantum DevOps.	4	5	3
Quantum testing	5	1	4
Quantum software interoperability.	2	2	5